

The Church of Christ, Agia Irini (Selino), Crete

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The Church of Christ, located just outside the village of Agia Irini near a stream, is a single nave church dated by inscription to 1357-58. A later narthex was added onto the west end of the church, and one enters the church through the southern wall of the narthex. Both the nave and the narthex have a pointed barrel vault interior and a saddle roof exterior. The church paintings are heavily damaged but mostly legible. Within the church sanctuary the apse is painted with the image of Christ Pantocrator above the images of two co-officiating bishops, St. John Chrysostom and St. Basil. The triumphal arch has an image of the Transfiguration above the apse and the scene of the Annunciation flanking the apse. The vault above the sanctuary shows the Ascension of Christ. The gallery of saints along the northern wall has the images of St. Stephen, St. Nicholas, and St. Polycarpus followed, past the paintings imitating a transverse arch, by three unidentified military saints on horseback. The southern wall gallery of saints has the images of an unidentified bishop, St. Eleutherius, the Archangel Michael, St. Marina (damaged by the placement of a later window), St. Paraskevi and St. Kyriaki. The barrel vault of the northern wall shows the Hypapante and the Baptism of Christ above and the Virgin blessed by the Priests and the Empty Sepulcher below. Similarly, the barrel vault of the southern side shows the Nativity above with Christ Anapeson and Christ appearing to the two Marys below. The western wall has a large image of the Crucifixion above some remaining scenes from the last judgment, particularly images of the damned and the Psychostasia on the southern side of the western door. To the northern side of the door are an unidentified military saint standing next to St. Mamas. The narthex possibly dates to the fifteenth century though the paintings are heavily damaged and the date cannot be determined with any accuracy. The eastern wall of the narthex includes an image of the Last Supper in the uppermost register above a small niche and doorway which once marked the entrance to the church. Four busts of female saints flank the niche in the second register. The doorway was once flanked by two saints, possibly military saints, but this cannot be determined with any certainty. Additional scenes from the life of Christ are located in the barrel vault without repeating any of the scenes located inside the nave. Two unidentified female saints can still be seen on the southern wall, west of the doorway but the remaining figures from the gallery of the saints have been lost. The western wall, also in a bad state of preservation with a later window opened onto this wall, has an image of the Koimesis (the Dormition of the Virgin) and the Archangel Michael. The church's dedicatory inscription (from the fourteenth-century paintings) mentions that the church was built and painted by the Orthodox Christians Ioannis Pattaktenis, his wife and children, Leon Pattaktenis, his wife, the monk Kostattios, Georgios Pattaktos, Georgios Pattaktenis and Kali in the Byzantine year 6866 (1357-58).

Date Range: 1357 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Agia Irini (Selino), Crete

Region tags: Crete, Greece

The church is located in the village of Agia Irini in the province of Selino on the island of Crete.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Spatharakis, Ioannis. Dated Byzantine Wall Paintings of Crete. Leiden: Alexandros Press, 2001., See p. 103-5, no. 36
- Source 2: Lymberopoulou, Angeliki, ed. Hell in the Byzantine World: A History of Art and Religion in Venetian Crete and the Eastern Mediterranean. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2020. See no. 9
- Source 3: Gerola, Giuseppe. Monumenti Veneti nell'isola di Creta. 4 vols. Venice: R. Istituto Veneto di Scienze, Lettere ed Arti, 1932. See Vol. IV, 465, no. 45

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

- I don't know

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Water source

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

- Yes

Type of feature

- Leveling of ground
- Clearing
- Trackway or road-surface

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

- No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

- Yes

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Other [specify]: Single nave chapel with a later narthex attached.

↳ One single feature

– Clearing

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:
– Other [specify]: Both.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
– Yes [specify]: Dedicated to Christ.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:
– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:
– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

– Other [specify]: According to the dedicatory inscription the church was built and painted by the Orthodox Christians Ioannis Pattaktenis, his wife and children, Leon Pattaktenis, his wife, the monk Kostattios, Georgios Pattaktos, Georgios Pattaktenis and Kali.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: plaster and stone.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

- ↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:
 - Yes

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

- ↳ Eyes (stylized or not)
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
 - No

- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife
 - Yes

- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)
 - No

- ↳ Humans
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural narratives
 - Yes

- ↳ Human narratives

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– I don't know

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– I don't know

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– I don't know

Are festivals present:

– I don't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The local Archaeological Service.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

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